

ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ШИПОВНИКА КАК ПРИРОДНОГО АНТИОКСИДАНТА

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7770826>

USES OF ROSEHIP AS A NATURAL ANTIOXIDANT

Annotation: Everyone knows that rosehip is a natural antioxidant, which is widely used in medicine. This is a plant of the Rose family, which has a rich vitamin composition and is widely used as a remedy.

Powerful antioxidants, which are rich in plant fruits, can slow down the aging process of cells and reduce the risk of developing cancer. It is believed that wild rose is a strong immunostimulating, bactericidal, anti-inflammatory and choleric agent.

Key words: rosehip, antioxidant, bactericide.

Introduction. It is believed that the birthplace of rosehip is the mountain slopes Iran and In the Himalayas, however, the shrub now grows in temperate and subtropical zones, and some of its species are found in the north up to the Arctic circle. It is known that the fruit of the plant was used for food at the end of the Ice Age in settlements in what is now Switzerland. People ate them raw and brewed tea. The medicinal properties of rosehip were well known in Ancient Greece and Rome, and later they were described by the famous scientist and doctor Avicenna. Rosehip is valued for the fact that its fruits contain 10 times more vitamin C than orange and lemon peels. They are also rich in vitamins P and K, flavonoids, carotenoids, tannins and pectins. Substances in its composition have analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects, accelerate tissue repair, reduce vascular permeability, have a positive effect on metabolism, increase the body's defenses against infections, and also stimulate mental and physical abilities. Rosehip fruit is a common medicinal raw material that is often used in medicine. In pharmacies, they are sold in dried form, as well as in the form of syrup, tablets, and extracts. In folk medicine, decoctions of rosehip were used for scarlet fever, typhoid, tuberculosis, inflammation of the kidneys, diseases of the intestines, liver, stomach. Rosehip roots in the form of a decoction are useful for malaria, urolithiasis, liver and spleen diseases, anorexia, diarrhea and dyspepsia. Seed oil of the plant helps with burns and dermatitis, trophic ulcers and radiation skin lesions. Decoction of seeds is considered a strong anti-inflammatory agent, helps with diarrhea and gingivitis. Rosehip branches and stems are used for rheumatism, sciatica, colds, stomach disorders, anemia, menstrual pain. Useful properties of rosehip help with flu and ARVI, as well as heart diseases — atherosclerosis, thrombosis, hypertension, and coronary heart disease. In all cases, the product is indicated as an adjunct to the main treatment prescribed by the doctor.

Rosehip is also popular as a component of cosmetics. It is often found in care products for oily, acne-prone, dry, sensitive and irritated skin. The vitamin composition of rosehip is rich. 100 grams of its fruit contain: 45% vitamin A, 18% vitamin B1, 24% vitamin E, 6% vitamin PP, 5%

vitamin B1. It has antioxidant properties (due to vitamins E and C). It protects the body from harmful substances.

It has a beneficial effect on liver cells, reduces the severity of inflammatory processes. Promotes the production of bile and cleaning the liver of toxins. Strengthens the immune system. This is achieved primarily due to the high concentration of vitamin C, as well as complex A and E. Therefore, it is used for frequent colds, the body's tendency to ARVI, as well as for the prevention of systemic infections. Reduces the total cholesterol level, thereby reducing the risk of many cardiovascular diseases. It is recommended for atherosclerosis, hypertension, coronary heart disease, and myocardial infarction. This applies to both treatment and prevention.

Reduces the risk of type II diabetes. By itself, rosehip does not treat diabetes mellitus. However, it provides better insulin absorption, which stabilizes glucose levels. Therefore, a decoction of its fruits is included in the treatment complex, as an auxiliary tool. It has analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect. Extract from wild rose fruits is beginning to be used to reduce pain in cases of musculoskeletal disorders. It accelerates the burning of adipose tissue and is recommended for those who are overweight.

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